

Assessment of the potential for microplastic retention in mature SUDS.

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ABSTRACT

1. Introduction.

Metropolitan regions and their environs comprise a dense gathering of inhabitants, infrastructure, and economic pursuits that demand significant resources and consequently, impose a severe strain on the environment. The process of urbanization, which is a significant contributor to climate change and pollution, modifies both living and non-living characteristics of ecosystems in and around urban areas, as well as those located far away from them (Grimm et al., 2008). The majority of people in the world live in cities. Currently, 74% of the European population resides in urban areas, and it is expected that this proportion will reach 80% by 2050 (according to AEMA in 2019). According to a recent evaluation of the Directive on Urban Wastewater Treatment, discharges of stormwater and overflows from combined sewer systems account for around 60% of the preventable organic pollution that is discharged into water bodies (Pistochi et al., 2019).

In environmental terms, one of the most critical and current challenges faced by entities responsible for managing stormwater is the issue of plastic pollution, particularly concerning microplastics (MPs), which are plastic particles measuring less than 5 mm. The pollution caused by MPs is one of the most pressing global environmental concerns, causing harm to ecosystems and reducing the services they provide to society. This is why the search for solutions to prevent their release into the environment and their degradation is crucial to address this issue.

Current urban areas are characterized by a high proportion of impermeable surfaces. As a result, during rainy periods, a large volume of surface runoff is generated, which flows towards the sanitation systems, many of which are combined. During particularly heavy rain periods, there is a high probability of combined sewer overflow (CSO). The discharge of CSO has an extremely adverse effect on the receiving environments. This is because they release mixtures of wastewater and stormwater, which can lead to problems of anoxia and eutrophication in the receiving water bodies, as well as the accumulation of debris (such as wipes, paper, and plastic) from both domestic wastewater and street litter. That is why new approaches are needed, such as nature-based solutions, to create new infrastructure that is multifunctional and provides multiple values, such as Sustainable Urban Drainage Systems (SUDS). SUDS have the ability to assist in managing flood risk and water quality. In addition, they can improve biodiversity and the livability of the urban environment (Raymond et al., 2017).

One of the main objectives of the research presented here is to analyze the long-term performance of mature SUDS in retaining MPs, from a hydrological and environmental perspective.

So far, much of the scientific research has been focused on evaluating the effectiveness of urban wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) in removing MPs and examining the fate of MPs throughout the various stages and components of WWTPs. However, there is limited research on runoff and nature-based solutions, such as SUDS, which can prevent the release of MPs into the environment. To date, only a few urban wetlands and bioretention systems for stormwater management have been evaluated and have demonstrated their ability to retain MPs (Mbachu et al., 2022).

In this case of study, vegetated swales will be specifically studied, which is a particular SUDS technology that consist of channels that are designed to store and/or transport surface water. They can be constructed to allow infiltration in suitable conditions. Their design should facilitate slow water flow, which aids in the

settling of suspended particles in stormwater runoff, leading to effective removal of pollutants. Swales along roadsides can be used instead of conventional drainage pipes and gullies (Woods-Ballard et al. 2015).

The purpose of this study is to examine the ability of mature vegetated swales, to remove MPs from urban runoff. To accomplish this task, two systems constructed over a decade ago in the municipality of Xàtiva, in the province of Valencia (Spain), will be evaluated (see Fig. 1).

Figure 1 | Current state of the vegetated swales under study. Left: North Roadway swale, right: Sport Area swale.

2. Methodology and results.

Soil and vegetation samples are being collected at various points of the infrastructure that are covered with vegetation in the areas alongside the road. They are then being examined to determine the quantity of MPs present. The information obtained will be used to assess the total amount of MPs that have accumulated in the infrastructure since its construction. The results distinguish between microplastics (MPs), particles smaller than 5 mm, mesoplastics (MEPs) (Fig. 3), particles ranging from 5 to 25 mm, and macroplastics (MAPs) (Fig. 2), all the large plastics found in different locations. Additionally, water samples that are representative of the inflow and outflow of the systems during different rain events will be collected. This will allow describing the behavior of water under these specific circumstances and comparing it to the findings on plastics in other studies of urban runoff.

Figure 2 | Macroplastics present *in situ* and those sampled in the laboratory for analysis at each sampling point.

Figure 3 | Mesoplastics collected in soil samples from the swales were isolated in glass jars for analysis (left). Microplastics were observed under a microscope in the soil samples: plastic fibers (center) and transparent particles (right).

Tables 1 and 2 present the results obtained regarding the analysis of MAPs, MEPs and MPs, respectively, found in soil samples.

Table 1 | Macroplastics and mesoplastics identified at each sampling point in the studied vegetated roadside swales. MEPs expressed as MPs per kilogram of dry soil weight.

Sample	MAPs Total	MAP/m2	MEPs/kg dw
SA1	27	4.5	8.50
SA2	27	4.5	200.83
SA3	65	5.2	20.38
NR1	20	6.67	11.81
NR2	116	38.67	22.24
NR3	10	3.33	343.17

Figure 4 | Total macroplastics found by type in both vegetated swales.

In this case, two different vegetated swales were studied, one located inside a sports complex named Sport Area (SA), and the other one located adjacent to a major road in the area, designated as North Roadway (NR) (see Fig. 1). At both sampling points, different areas within the swale were identified, including an initial area (point 1) located at the top, an intermediate area (point 2), and a final area (point 3) located near the outlet chambers for both SUDS. One noteworthy point is the intermediate area (point 2) of the NR ditch, which is located next to a unique element installed in the ditch, a discontinuous wall designed to allow pedestrian access and to create a backwater for the water flow. The gaps in the wall allow water to flow through, but the walls themselves act as significant plastic retention structures, as evidenced by the large number of MAPs collected at this sampling point (see central image in Figure 2). Furthermore, point 3 of the SA swale, located at the end of the swale's own pipeline and where a retention pool is formed before entering the final chamber, has a much larger collection surface for plastics, making it a potentially significant retention point for them.

Regarding the overall percentages of MAPs found, the presence of packaging stands out as the main category, representing 72.5% of the total samples (see Fig. 4), while bottles constitute a significant 12.5% of the total. These findings are consistent with global plastic production data, which indicate that 44% of plastic production is intended for packaging, being the largest category of production, followed by plastics used in construction and building, which represent 18% of production and may also be contributing to the category of wrappers found in the samples (PlasticsEurope, 2021).

Table 2 | Microplastics found in the various sampled soil points of the studied vegetated ditches and expressed as MPs per kilogram of dry soil weight.

Sample	Fibers	Films	Particles	MPs/kg dw
SA1	10	0	15	4533.62
SA2	10	20	4	7412.45
SA3	16	1	1	3545.34
NR1	5	3	9	3218.82
NR2	6	2	4	2300.49
NR3	10	2	4	3147.25

As shown in Table 2, it can be observed that fibers are the most commonly found shape among all samples. This could be attributed to their greater mobility when exposed to environmental agents such as wind or water flow within the roadside ditches. Additionally, there is no direct relationship observed between MAPs and MPs, as a considerable amount of time may elapse in the plastic cycle before macroplastics become microplastics. The most contaminated soil was found in the vegetated swale of the Sports Area, which was expected to have lower concentrations given that it is an area less exposed to traffic and also enclosed by a fence facing the street. It is worth noting that many of the MAPs found in the vegetated swale of North Roadway, particularly in zone 2, came directly from construction worksites adjacent to the ditch (i.e., cement bags, paint cans, construction product containers).

Conclusion.

The initial results of this study highlight the importance of the problem associated with the presence of microplastics in urban runoff. A significant amount of these contaminants has been observed in SUDS infrastructure built more than ten years ago, indicating that urban runoff is a significant source of microplastics. The next steps of the research will focus on assessing the potential of these nature-based solutions to retain and biodegrade microplastics, with the ultimate goal of preventing their progression towards receiving bodies.

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